

PROBLEMS ARISING IN CONSUMER CHOICE AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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ANNOTATION . Today, the impact of consumer choice on our country's markets as well as the global market is significant. This article evaluates the influence and position of consumer choice in the process of entering domestic and global markets for goods and services. It also examines the issues that arise in consumer choice and possible solutions to address them.

KEY WORDS: Utility , Total utility (TU), Marginal utility (MU), Util , Goods, Law of diminishing marginal utility , Good, Bad, Indifference curve, Consumer, Income, Demand.

The theory of consumer choice is the branch of microeconomics that relates preferences to consumption expenditures and to consumer demand curves. It analyzes how consumers maximize the desirability of their consumption, by maximizing utility subject to a consumer budget constraint.¹

Consumer theory shows individuals make choices given their income and the prices of goods and services. There are two main theories of consumer choice which are the ordinalist or indifference curve approach and the cardinalist or marginal utility approach.²

How do consumers make decisions about what to buy ?

Where does the Demand curve come from?

#They consider preferences and budget

#Maximize utility subject to budget constraint

EXAMPLE:

- A consumer has an income of \$1000 per month to spend on pizza and coke.
- The price of a pizzais \$ 10.
- The price of a litre of coke is \$2

-If the consumer spends all of his income on pizza ,he can buy 100 pizzas per month .

-If the consumer spends all of his income on litres of Coke , he can buy 500litres per month.

Using this information ,we can draw the consumer's budget constraint the first graph:

Consumer choice example in graph

- The slope of the budget constraint equals the relative price of the two goods.

TOTAL AND MARGINAL UTILITY

Goods are desired because of their ability to satisfy human wants. The property of a good that enables it satisfy human wants is called utility. As individuals consume more of a good per time period, their total utility(TU) or satisfaction increases, but their marginal utility diminishes. Marginal utility(MU) is the extra utility received from consuming one additional unit of the good per unit of time holding constant the quantity consumed of all other commodities.

For example, First table indicates that one hamburger per day (or, more generally, one unit of good X per period of time) gives a consumer a total utility(TU) of 10

utils, where a util is an arbitrary unit of utility. Total utility increases with each additional hamburger consumed until the fifth one, which leaves total utility unchanged. This is the saturation point. Consuming the sixth hamburger then leads to a decline in total utility because of storage or disposal problems. The third column of our table gives the extra or marginal utility resulting from the consumption of each additional hamburger. Marginal utility is positive but declines until the fifth hamburger, for which it is zero, and becomes negative for the sixth hamburger.

Q	TU	MU
0	0	...
1	10	10
2	16	6
3	20	4
4	22	2
5	22	0
6	20	-2

Total and marginal utility

The first table: TOTAL AND MARGINAL Utility. In the top panel, total utility (TU) increases by smaller and smaller amounts (the shaded areas) and so the marginal utility (MU) in the bottom panel declines. TU remains unchanged with the consumption of the fifth hamburger, and so MU is zero. After the fifth hamburger per day, TU declines and MU is negative.

Plotting the values given in our table, we obtain Figure our table, with the top panel showing total utility and the bottom panel showing marginal utility. The total and marginal utility curves are obtained by joining the midpoints of the bars measuring TU and MU at each level of consumption. Note that the TU rises by smaller and smaller amounts (the shaded areas) and so the MU declines. The consumer reaches saturation after consuming the fourth hamburger. Thus, remains

unchanged with the consumption of the fifth hamburger and MU is zero. After the fifth hamburger TU declines and MU is negative. The negative slope or downward-to-the-right inclination of the MU curve reflects the law of diminishing marginal utility.

Utility schedules reflect tastes of a particular individual; that is they are unique to the individual and reflect his or her own particular subjective preferences and perceptions. Different individuals may have different tastes and different utility schedules. Utility schedules remain unchanged so long as the individual's tastes remain the same.³

Consumers' tastes can be examined with ordinal measure of utility is based on three assumptions. First, we assume that when faced with any two baskets of goods, the consumer can determine whether he or she prefers basket A to B, B to A, or whether he or she is indifferent between the two. Second, we assume that the tastes of consumer are consistent or transitive. That is, if the consumer states that he or she prefers basket A to B and also that he or she prefers basket B to basket C, then that consumer will prefer A to C. Third, we assume that more of a commodity is preferred to less; that the commodity is a good rather than bad, and the consumer is never satiated with the commodity. The three assumptions can be used to represent an individual's tastes with indifference curves. In order to conduct the analysis by plane geometry, we will assume throughout that there are only two goods, X and Y.

An indifference curve shows the various combinations of two goods that give the consumer equal utility or satisfaction. A higher indifference curve refers to a higher level of satisfaction, and a lower indifference curve refers to less satisfaction, and a lower indifference curve refers to less satisfaction. However, we have no indicators. That is, different indifference curves simply provide an ordering or ranking of the individual's preference.⁴

For example, in our second table gives us an indifference schedule showing the various combinations of hamburgers (good X) and soft drinks (good Y) that

give the consumer equal satisfaction . This information plotted as indifference curve U_1 in the left panel of figure in our table. The right panel repeats indifference curve U_1 along with a higher indifference curve (U_2) and a lower one (U_0). Indifference curve U_1 shows that one hamburger and ten soft drinks per unit of time (combination A) give the consumer the same level of satisfaction as two hamburgers and six soft drinks (combination B), four hamburgers and three soft drinks (Combination C), or seven hamburgers and one soft drink (combination F). On the other hand, combination R (Four hamburgers and seven soft drinks) has both more hamburgers and more soft drinks than combination B (see the right panel of figure in our table), and so it refers to a higher level of satisfaction. Thus, combination R and all the other combinations that give the same level of satisfaction as combination R define higher indifference curve U_2 .

Finally, all combinations on U_0 give the same satisfaction as combination T, and combination T refers to both fewer hamburgers and fewer soft drinks than (and therefore is inferior to) combination B on U_1 .

Hamburgers (X)	Soft Drinks (Y)	Combinations
1	10	A
2	6	B
4	3	C
7	1	F

Indifference schedule

Although in Figure in second table we have drawn only three indifference curves , there is an indifference curve going through each point in the XY plane (referring to each possible combination of good X and good Y). That is, between any two indifference curves, an additional curve can always be drawn. The entire set of indifference curves is called an indifference map and reflects the entire set of tastes and preferences of the consumer.⁵

Conclusion. The theory of consumer choice plays a significant role in the increase of demand and the improvement of product quality. Manufacturers also consider their production levels and the quality of their products based on the theoretical concept of consumer choice. As we live in a modern era where information technology and science are advancing, it is essential for today's consumers to deeply understand the consumer choice in a way that also reflects modernization and complexity.

In order to impact the consumer choice, it is necessary to pay attention to the factors influencing the selection and the decline of consumer surplus. Therefore, production should be designed and executed in response to contemporary demands, focusing on the design and quality of goods.

Consumer choice can be a force competing with quality, as a consumer's first impression of a product may not be favorable, but when other consumers who have purchased the product second the opinion, it becomes an advantage for the increasing sales of the new product.

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